

Reliability of the Sensbalance Mini Board as an Assessment Tool for Balance and Proprioception Measures

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ARTICLE INFO

©2025 RS Publication

Paper ID: IJPHC-68A5AAF2D2510

Received: 2025-07-23

Published: 2025-08-23

DOI:

<https://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16932926>

Page No: 167-176

ABSTRACT

Background: Balance is the ability to maintain the body's center of gravity over its base of support, whether moving or still. It involves postural stability and is essential for assessing recovery and fall risk. Balance relies on coordination between the vestibular system, vision, and somatosensory feedback, including proprioception and tactile input.

Objective: This study aimed to assess inter-rater and intra-rater reliability of balance and proprioception using the Sensbalance mini board.

Methods and Materials: In this study, a 10° spherical rubber attachment secured the sensbalance mini board. A total of 162 participants stood barefoot in a consistent position for all trials. They removed footwear, stood upright with arms at sides, and maintained a relaxed posture while looking at a 60-second countdown on a laptop. No proprioceptive feedback was given. Each participant completed four sessions—two with each investigator—with a one-day rest between sessions conducted by the same investigator to ensure consistency.

Results: Among 162 participants, 11% were male and 89% female. Intra-rater reliability for balance showed ICCs of 0.253 and 0.02; for proprioception, 0.057 and 0.073. Inter-rater reliability showed low ICCs: 0.007 for balance and 0.057 for proprioception, indicating generally poor reliability across both assessors and measurement types.

Conclusion: The study found that balance and proprioception utilizing the Sensbalance small board has low intra- and inter-rater reliability. Future research could be conducted with the potential confounding factors controlled. Using reliable outcome instruments is important in evaluating clinical change.

Keywords: Balance, Proprioception, Assessment tool, Sensbalance mini board, Postural control

Cite This Paper: Prerana Saravanan, M. Saravanan, Jadav Dharmistha, Kalsariya Nilesh, Kathiriya Shival and Khunt Vandana (2025). "Reliability of the Sensbalance Mini Board as an Assessment Tool for Balance and Proprioception Measures". *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCE AND HEALTH CARE (IJPHC)* ISSN 2249 – 5738, vol. 15, no. 5, 2025, pp. 167-176. DOI: <https://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16932926>

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INTRODUCTION

Balance refers to the capacity to uphold a steady posture for the longest time possible with the least amount of body movement or the capability to keep the body's center of gravity aligned over its base of support [1]. Balance, also known as postural stability, refers to the broad process through which the body maintains its position in a stable state, whether at rest (static equilibrium) or in motion (dynamic equilibrium) [2]. A balance assessment offers valuable insights crucial for setting benchmarks to evaluate a person's functional recovery and to forecast the likelihood of falls [3].

The proprioceptive system operates through the mechanoreceptive senses, including touch, pressure, vibration, and tickle, all of which are collectively known as the tactile senses, as well as the sense of position that assesses the relative locations and movement speeds of different body parts. Muscle spindles and Golgi tendon sensory receptors (known as proprioceptors) are essential for the nervous system's regulation of posture. They offer constant feedback to the nervous system regarding the current state of every muscle. Stretch receptors located within the muscle track muscle length and any changes in that length. Golgi tendon organs (GTO) are situated in the tendons at their connection with muscles and function as a second category of afferent receptor (proprioceptors). They transmit information regarding the tension within the muscle or the rate at which that tension changes [4].

A complicated motor function, postural control is produced by integrating multiple neural components, such as movement and sensory strategies, spatial orientation, biomechanical restrictions, and cognitive processing [5]. There are numerous tools for evaluating balance. Utilizing tools like the Timed Get Up & Go Test [6], the Tinetti Performance Oriented Mobility Assessment [7] & Berg Balance test [8]. Even in the absence of any technology, these instruments are employed as subjective evaluation techniques. Some academics have underlined the necessity of creating new evaluation instruments in order to get around issues like the ceiling effect that the earlier instruments had. A tool called the Force Platform is used in labs to quantitatively measure balance [9]. Force platform tests are typically conducted in a static state. Body sway due to a variety of factors can explain balance [10]. Force platform procedures take a lot of time and are difficult to move since they are more expensive.

A vital component of daily living tasks is balance. Multiple neural pathways must communicate in order to maintain balance. The interaction of at least three sensory information sources—the vestibular system, the visual brain, and the somatosensory system (proprioception, kinesthesia) is referred to as the postural control system when describing how one maintains balance [11].

A commonly used instrument to measure postural control is Nintendo Wii which is widely used both clinically and for research purposes. There has been a lot of interest in the use of the Nintendo Wii balance board (WBB) as a tool for measuring postural control in the fields of fundamental, clinical, and rehabilitation research. Despite being suggested as a substitute for the "gold standard" laboratory-grade force plate, more investigation is required before the WBB can be regarded as a legitimate and trustworthy center of pressure (CoP) measurement tool. All things considered, balance is a complicated system that combines vestibular, visual, and somatosensory systems to accomplish movement objectives in daily life and athletic activities. According to research, maintaining appropriate balance involves a variety of factors, including muscular activity and central nervous system communication. It can be easier to comprehend how balance is evaluated using various balance tools if you know how it is attained and maintained. Balance can

be seen as a well-structured reflexive process when the synergies and tactics are understood. This is crucial because when balance issues occur, one of the system's components is disrupted, making it unable to precisely adapt to disturbances and preserve equilibrium [12].

There is paucity of evidence for the sensbalance mini board as a reliable balance assessment tool for clinical and/or research usage, the significance of this study is to provide substantial evidence of whether the sensbalance mini board can be used as a reliable balance assessment tool. This study aims to use a sensbalance mini board for assessing reliability through balance & proprioceptive measures. No studies are available which assesses balance &/or proprioception using sensbalance mini board till date.

Sensamove is a young, dynamic and innovative company that develops and produces interactive exercise equipment. Sensamove wants to encourage exercising by giving useful visual bio-feedback, making therapy more fun, and its results are readily measurable. The Sensbalance Mini Board is a new, interactive piece of training equipment with meaningful exercise software, easy-to-understand measuring software and exciting game software. Based on the conventional wobble board and made even more applicable for effective training of physical balance, reflexes, proprioception and core stability. It can be used for therapy, prevention and fitness. (info@sensamove.com)

The Sensbalance Mini Board combines the interactive training software and exercise games with the well-known benefits of a conventional wobble board. This results in an innovative and very effective new product in the range of interactive balance products of Sensamove. With easy exchangeable accessories the tilting angle and exercise difficulty can be customized. This makes the Mini board a widely applicable training and therapy tool. (www.sensamove.com)

The purpose of this study was to evaluate the reliability of the sensbalance mini board as an assessment tool for balance & proprioception. The study aims to determine inter-rater & intra-rater reliability of balance and proprioception measures using Sensbalance mini board.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The purpose of this reliability study was to evaluate the reliability of the sensbalance mini board as an assessment tool for balance & proprioception on healthy individuals. The information obtained from this study can provide evidence about how much reliable the sensbalance mini board is in detecting one's balance & proprioception. This study involved 162 apparently healthy physiotherapy students (18 males and 144 females) with age between 18-26 years from The Sarvajanic College of Physiotherapy by convenient sampling method. Participants with musculoskeletal injuries in previous three months, pregnancy and subjects who are currently taking medication that could alter sensory perception were excluded from the study.

Instrument used: Sensbalance Mini Board

The Sensbalance Mini Board combines the interactive training software and exercise games with the well-known benefits of a conventional wobble board. With easy exchangeable accessories the tilting angle and exercise difficulty can be customized. This makes the Mini board a widely applicable training and therapy tool.

Figure: 1. Sensbalance mini board with rubber sphere of 10° .

Features of the Mini Board:

- Wooden wobble board (diameter: 40 cm / 15.7 inches).
- Made of high quality birch with anti-slip coating.
- Easy exchangeable rubber accessories using a magnetic click-on system.
- Includes a standard spherical rubber accessory of 10° .
- Optional spherical accessories of 15° / 20° , and one-directional accessory of 15°
- Integrated sensor for registering tilts.
- Standard USB connection cable or optional Wireless Module.
- Including basic exercise software with measuring & archiving functions, for diagnosis and comparison purposes, to show improvements over time.
- Balance game with 18 Training exercises and 10 exciting Easy levels.

Sensbalance Measuring & Exercise Software:

The Sensbalance Measuring & Exercise Software shows the sensor signal as a red cursor within concentric circles on the screen either during or right after the exercises. By seeing the tilting results real-time on the screen the users can easily and effectively train neuromuscular control by correcting and improving their exercise movements on the fly. The sensitivity of the sensor is adjustable. This enables dedicated mobility or stability training. Movement trajectories can be measured and saved for future reference.

Data collection included two assessors assessing 162 participants. All the subjects were tested under the same condition. Before the measurement, general information about the

participants was collected including their age through personal interview. Height & weight of the participants were taken using calibrated instruments.

In this study sensbalance mini board was attached with a standard spherical rubber accessory of 10°. Participants were instructed to stand on the sensbalance mini board with their bare foot in the same place to ensure consistent placement across trials. Participants were asked to remove their shoes & socks and stand upright on the sensbalance mini board & remain as still as possible in a relaxed posture. Participants were asked to put their arms to their sides in a comfortable position & to distribute their body weight evenly on both the feet while breathing normally. Then, the participants were asked to look straight ahead where lap top screen was facing in front of them indicating completion of 60 seconds time. Visual feedback was provided for assessing balance on laptop screen but for proprioception no feedback on screen was provided.

Figure: 2. Sensbalance mini board attached with laptop

In each session participants followed the procedure mentioned above till standing on a sensbalance mini board & then 1st balance was checked. Once participants confirmed their comfort managing themselves on sensbalance mini board, it was calibrated. They were asked to maintain a red cursor within concentric circles on the screen. This process continued for 60 seconds. After

this procedure the participants were asked to get down from the balance board. Immediately after recording its reading for the balance, the participants were asked to stand again on the sensbalance mini board for proprioception test. In this test 1st visual cue as a red cursor was provided to the participants for the judgment. Once participants confirmed their comfort managing themselves on sensbalance mini board, it was calibrated. As soon as the recording started for proprioception, no visual cue on screen was provided. This procedure continued for 60 seconds. Then the findings of proprioception test were recorded.

The participants were scheduled for 4 sessions. Two sessions were conducted with each of the investigators. In each session, the assessor had taken balance first and then proprioception. There was a rest of one day for the participants between the sessions of the same investigator. At the end of test the result of the test taken by the first assessor for the balance for the first time was recorded as S1B1 & the first assessor assessing balance for the second time was recorded as S2B2. At the end of the test, the result of the test taken by the second assessor for the balance for the first time was recorded as V1B1 & the second assessor assessing balance for the second time was recorded as V2B2. Same way, proprioception assessed by the first assessor for the first time was recorded as S1P1 & proprioception assessed by the first assessor for the second time was recorded as S2P2. Proprioception test carried out by the second assessor for the first time was recorded as V1P1 & proprioception assessed by the second assessor for the second time was recorded as V2P2.

RESULTS

Statistical analysis was carried out using SPSS version 20. Statistical analysis included testing of intraclass correlation coefficient (ICC) for the reliability. Both the intra-rater & inter-rater reliability was assessed statistically with 95% of confidence interval & $p < 0.05$.

Graph: 1. Frequency Distribution of Gender among participants

Graph: 2. Mean values of Age, height, weight and Body Mass Index (BMI) among participants

Table: 1. Intraclass Correlation Coefficient of Balance Performance by Assessor 1 on Two Different Occasions (S1B1 & S2B2)

	Intraclass Correlation	95% Confidence Interval		F Test with True Value 0			
		Lower Bound	Upper Bound	Value	df1	df2	Sig
Single Measures	.253	.103	.391	1.676	161	162	.001
Average Measures	.403	.187	.562	1.676	161	162	.001

Table: 2. Intraclass Correlation Coefficient of Balance Performance by Assessor 2 on Two Different Occasions (V1B1-V2B2)

	Intraclass Correlation	95% Confidence Interval		F Test with True Value 0			
		Lower Bound	Upper Bound	Value	df1	df2	Sig
Single Measures	.002	-.151	.156	1.004	161	162	.489
Average Measures	.004	-.357	.269	1.004	161	162	.489

Table: 3. Intraclass Correlation Coefficient of Proprioception Performance by Assessor 1 on Two Different Occasions (S1P1-S2P2)

	Intraclass Correlation	95% Confidence Interval		F Test with True Value 0			
		Lower Bound	Upper Bound	Value	df1	df2	Sig
Single Measures	-.057	-.209	.097	.891	161	162	.767
Average Measures	-.122	-.529	.177	.891	161	162	.767

Table: 4. Intraclass Correlation Coefficient of Proprioception Performance by Assessor 2 on Two Different Occasions (V1P1-V2P2)

	Intraclass Correlation	95% Confidence Interval		F Test with True Value 0			
		Lower Bound	Upper Bound	Value	df1	df2	Sig
Single Measures	.073	-.081	.224	1.157	161	162	.177
Average Measures	.136	-.177	.366	1.157	161	162	.177

Table: 5. Interclass Correlation Coefficient of Balance Performance between Two Assessors (S1B1-V1B1)

	Intraclass Correlation	95% Confidence Interval		F Test with True Value 0			
		Lower Bound	Upper Bound	Value	df1	df2	Sig
Single Measures	-.007 ^a	-.161	.147	.985	161	161	.538
Average Measures	-.015	-.384	.256	.985	161	161	.538

Table: 6. Interclass Correlation Coefficient of Proprioception Performance between Two Assessors (S1P1-V1P1)

	Intraclass Correlation	95% Confidence Interval		F Test with True Value 0			
		Lower Bound	Upper Bound	Value	df1	df2	Sig
Single Measures	-.057 ^a	-.209	.098	.893	161	161	.764
Average Measures	-.120	-.527	.179	.893	161	161	.764

DISCUSSION

Many studies had been already done using different instruments for measuring balance & proprioception in the past. Majority of studies used force platform as a tool for measuring the balance. There is paucity of literature on mini board which measure balance & proprioception using the wobble balance board called Sensbalance mini board. Considering poor evidence available with this balance board, this study was designed for the purpose of checking inter-rater & intra-rater reliability. The purpose of this reliability study was to evaluate the reliability of the sensbalance mini board as an assessment tool for balance & proprioception on healthy individuals. The information obtained from this study can provide evidence about how much reliable the sensbalance mini board is in detecting one's balance & proprioception.

The study was conducted at the premises of The Sarvajanic College of Physiotherapy with 162 physiotherapy students volunteering to be part of the study from the same college. Study criteria & specifications were tried to be maintained same for both the assessors during each test. General demographic characteristics like their gender, age, height, weight & BMI were included as part of the study. Graph: 1 suggests that out of total (n=162) participants, 11% (n=18) were male & 89% (n=144) were females. Mean values of age, height, weight & body mass index (BMI) is represented by graph: 2. Age of the participants was represented with the mean age 20.22years (SD ± 1.921). Age varied between the lower limit 17 to the upper limit 26 among the 162 participants. Height of the participants was represented as mean height 158.77cm (SD ± 6.805). Weight of the participants was shown in the graph with mean weight 55.2KG (SD ± 12.848). Out of 162 participants mean BMI was 21.84 (SD ± 64.61) with the highest being 44.91 & lowest being 13.85.

The study targeted both the inter-rater & intra-rater reliability of balance & proprioceptive measures for the participants participated in the study. The tool used i.e. sensbalance mini board

for assessing balance & proprioception provides many options for different tests. This study was carried out using balance as one & proprioception as the second assessing tests. In balance five items were recorded in the result. Balance was assessed in front, back, left & right separately for each second for 60 seconds. The performance percentage was given in the result indicating the overall performance of balance. Similarly, the proprioception was assessed in front, back, left & right separately for each second for 60 seconds. The performance percentage was given in the result indicating the overall performance of the proprioception.

In the intra-rater reliability of balance tested by the first assessor as per table: 1, Intraclass Correlation Coefficient (ICC) of S1B1 & S2B2 is 0.253 at 95 % of confidence interval which suggested poor reliability for assessing balance. Table: 2 suggest the intra-rater reliability of balance performed by the second assessor as per Intraclass Correlation Coefficient (ICC) of V1B1 & V2B2 is 0.02. This is suggestive of poor reliability of balance performance of second assessor. The statistical results reveal that the intra-rater reliability of balance performance for the first assessor & that of second assessor was poor.

In the intra-rater reliability of proprioception tested by the first assessor as per table: 3, Intraclass Correlation Coefficient (ICC) of S1P1 & S2P2 is 0.057 at 95 % of confidence interval. The result of table: 3 suggest that the intra-rater reliability of proprioception assessed by the first assessor was poor. The intra-rater reliability of proprioception performed by the second assessor as per Intraclass Correlation Coefficient (ICC) of V1P1 & V2P2 is 0.073 as shown in table: 4. This is suggestive of poor intra-rater reliability of proprioceptive performance of second assessor. Intra-rater reliability of first assessor & second assessor for the proprioception performance was poor.

The study also included inter-rater reliability of both the balance & proprioception. For assessing the inter-rater reliability the first measures of balance & proprioception for both the assessor was taken. Inter-rater reliability of balance represented as S1B1 & V1B1 as per Intraclass Correlation Coefficient (ICC) is 0.007 which is shown in table: 5. The result is suggestive of very poor inter-rater reliability. Table: 6 represent the inter-rater reliability of proprioception as per Intraclass Correlation Coefficient (ICC) is 0.057. The result signifies that the inter-rater reliability of proprioception is poor.

The overall results of both intra-rater & inter-rater reliability for balance & proprioception is poor. There are many factors responsible for any study findings to be less reliable. The sensbalance mini board has multiple testing procedures, but this study included only two tests as balance performance & proprioception performance.

Reliability is a scientific term that is frequently used in clinical practice, yet its relationship to measurement error is often not well understood. All therapy and rehabilitation measurements involve error and it is the responsibility of the clinician to reduce these errors as much as possible, particularly those that are random in nature. This is required to produce a measurement that is close as possible to its true value. Reliability, however, is not just a scientific phenomenon. In the clinical setting it is imperative to have an understanding of measurement errors— both those which may be attributed to the clinician and those related to the measurement instrument— so that the extent of true change in patient status can be identified [13].

CONCLUSION

The study concluded that the intra-rater & inter-rater reliability of balance & proprioception using sensbalance mini board is significantly poor. There are many factors responsible for poor reliability. Future study may be carried out with following changes &

controlling the possible confounding factors. Using reliable outcome instruments is important in evaluating clinical change. Measurement error and reliability testing are key concepts underpinning outcome instrument reliability. A range of strategies should be used for minimizing measurement error.

Future recommendation:

As there is paucity of literature for this study, before concluding poor reliability, future study should be considered. Future study can be encouraged by using direct observation in four areas.

- 1) Methods to evaluate reliability.
- 2) Instrument content & design.
- 3) Observer training.
- 4) Data collection.

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